

SUFFERING OF FEMALE AUTHORS FROM THE UNFAIR TREATMENT OF THE SYSTEM AND SOCIETY

Khosiast Rustamova

Independent researcher of Termiz State University

E-mail: avgust-07@list.ru

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Abstract

Creative experience gave rise to new styles, especially modernist approaches to the expression of reality. In recent years, it has become prominent for researchers to study the specific styles in the works of female and male authors. This article discusses the fate of poetry and the unfair attitude towards the work of female artists in society. Also, the poetry and life details of Anna Akhmatova, a major representative of Russian literature, are analyzed.

Key words: poet, woman, oppression, violence, society, rebellion, oppression and fate.

Modern literary studies today require researchers to study each period in depth and detail. Such a deep approach is necessary for the analysis of Russian Silver Age literature, which played a major role in world literature. But this period introduced many writers and poets and also exposed them to many trials. The tragedies in their lives gave artists the courage to rebel against the times, events, political changes in society and the priority system, and to change the order of society. The introduction of modernism in literature made it possible to realize the importance of real discoveries in all aspects of fiction. Yu. Eichenwald, I. Annensky, V. Bryusov, V. Zhirmunsky, V. Ivanov, S. Makovsky, O. Mandelstam, N. Otsup, I. Severyanin, B. Among artists like Eichenbaum, they are among the most prominent representatives of modernism. Akhmatova's work, which consists of difficult and painful experiences, shows the uniqueness, uniqueness and attractiveness of the poet's personality. Commonalities and imbalances in the psyche of men and women form the basis of creativity. "I taught women to speak," says the poet himself in one of his appeals. The poet had sufficient grounds for such a claim. Because his literature was suppressed by the regime in his time, and his literature reflected a strong rebellion against violence. Anna Akhmatova's life is like one of the unfathomable mysteries of female endurance and tenacity. The responsibility of living in a very difficult, conflicting and turbulent time fell to the end of the poetess. Two world wars... the revolution, along with many fates, turned his life upside down. The death of loved ones, imprisonment, loss, persecution, and oppression left indelible wounds in the poet's heart. At this point, we found it necessary to mention a tragedy that

happened in the life of this artist. In one of her poems depicting historical tragedies, Anna Andreevna Akhmatova implored people to say: "My husband is in the grave, my son is not alive - pray for me." Because not only the beautiful feelings of the poetess, but also the delicate body are mercilessly trampled under the heels of violent times: her husband Nikolay Gumilyov was shot by the Bolsheviks in 1921 [1].

It was not easy for the poet even in the years after the war. In 1946, by the decision of the Central Committee of the Communist Party, he was politically condemned and removed from the membership of the Union of Writers for the series of poems published in the Znamya magazine. His poems and books were banned[2].

System did not spare her son Lev Gumilyov either, look at the joke of fate, the young man was thrown into prison by the Bolsheviks... On November 6, 1949 (on purpose, the day before the holiday!), the investigator visited Anna Akhmatova's apartment with a soft bark and said: "Ma'am, search your house and we will take your son to prison," he said, then took out a warrant from a leather folder. The search has begun. "Grajdanka Akhmatova"'s personal belongings, rags and rags can be seen from the water. Humiliated and insulted, Anna Akhmatova's nerves were cut. When they drove away with her only son whom they had wished for, the poetess burned all her manuscripts, unpublished poems and epics without leaving a single one! [3]

This time, Lev Gumilyov will be deprived of his freedom for ten years.

The 70th anniversary of "Dohi" is approaching. Anna Akhmatova, who was devastated, was given a friendly advice by "some comrades": "Please, write a hymn! After all, even in the past, poets wrote odes in the name of kings!" says, guides...

For the first time in her life, Akhmatova deviated from her creative principle and wrote two poems in praise of Stalin (those poems were immediately published in the Ogonyok magazine and appeared in the world). The reason why Akhmatova's series, whose poems have not been published in the Shura press for ten to fifteen years, appeared one after another in the Ogonyok magazine, certainly means that the "social order" came down from the top. However, Stalin still did not release Lev Gumilyov, the son of a poet, despite all the sufferings of fate... Even this did not break the proud poet. In 1951, he was reinstated as a member of the association. Finally, in 1955, the poet was given a field house in the town of Komarovo.

In this way, rebellion against the society that humiliates women was awakened in the poet's heart. Anna Akhmatova wanted to be called a poet rather than a poetess, biographers assure. Due to these demands of female poets, the greatness of talent, the scale of the task and the importance of living beyond oneself began to be studied [4]. Where did this principle come from? Women's poetry of the 20th century was not taken seriously. In the 1910s, women's works were approached with the following critical opinions: "Woman's pen", "Love and Suspicion" and the label "incomplete" was attached to them. Therefore, the word "poetessa" (poet) sounded like a mocking word. Zinaida Gippius, for example, wrote her works on behalf of men, with one goal - to be taken seriously. Many women published their poems under male pseudonyms. In fact, because of this problem, the roles of men and women in society began to be studied in literature, linguistics, art, and philosophy [5]. It should be said that psychoanalytical methods contributed to the development of literature. Researchers who have studied the issue of gender say that representatives of this issue attach great importance to personal life. Such examples can also be found in Russian literature.

When studying the essence of feminist views, one should not forget to study the gender differences, the biography of the author, other writers who influenced his work, as well as the socio-cultural situation of the time when the creator lived [6]. For example, during the period of Anna Akhmatova, the iron policy put many people under pressure, it is no secret that during the Stalin era, the intellectuals were mainly persecuted, they suffered from this and faced injustices. In any case, the harsh blows of the regime played a major role in the creation of poets and writers and nurtured a creative personality. It is not wrong to say that this brutal tyranny separated the star from the night. In the following lines, it is not difficult to see how deep the poet's suffering is.

От странной лирики,
Где каждый шаг - секрет,
Где пропасти налево и направо,
Где под ногой, как лист увядший, слава,
По-видимому, мне спасенья нет [7].

(From an unnatural lyric, every step is hidden, there are ravines like a leaf that takes fame to the left and to the right. It seems to me that there is no safety.) It can be seen from the poem that the poet wrote in depression for a while that time has made him suffer a lot, she was a woman, therefore how much he suffered in society. Whether he likes it or not, in this situation, the dark pages of

his life appear in the lines of his works. Pain in his poems is often based on biographical factors.

Akhmatova tried to prove the wrong idea that "being a poet is stupid for a woman" in her entire work [8]. The poet was right in his attempt, because considering three centuries, the names of women in Russian literature can be counted by hand, and none of them can compare to Anna Akhmatova's depth of thoughts, poetic talent, and strength of feelings. But he had to fight for a long time to gain the right to be a poet [9]:

Нет, царевич, я не та,
Кем меня ты видеть хочешь,
И давно мои уста
Не целуют, а пророчат.
(No, my prince, not me,
What you want to see
My lips for a long time
A kiss does not give a gift, but prophesies.)

Through these lines, Anna Akhmatova expresses that she is trying to realize that she has left the happiness of ordinary womanhood and devoted her life to poetry. Unlike Marina, Akhmatova can imagine her muse in the form of a woman, when Muza did not receive a message, there was no happier person in the world than her:

И - я не могу взлететь,
А с детства была крылатой.
(Despite the fact that I was born with wings from childhood, I cannot fly). This is actually the lament of a captive poet, tired of the violence of his time, squeezed by being put in a cage.

The pain of lack of inspiration completely destroyed the poet, who was tired of the same life, full of thoughts in the same torment of pain. In one line, he writes "Muza ushlyta po doroge", Akhmatova writes: When the fairy of inspiration leaves, for the poet the earth is too narrow, as if it seems like a grave where it is impossible to breathe, and "zhizn, kajetsya, visit na voloske" (life is like a strand of hair seems to be hanging), Anna Akhmatova forgets all fame, freedom, youth, pleasure, looking forward to the expected blessing from the heavens, every day of her life was a poison-wound, the poet declares this in this way:

Как и жить мне с этой обузой,
А еще называют Музой,
Говорят: "Ты с ней на лугу..."

Говорят: "Божественный лепет..."

Жестче, чем лихорадка, оттреплет,

И опять весь год ни гу-гу.

(As I live with this burden, they say: you are on the hill with it, they say: these are divine whispers, The pain is heavier than the fever, and another year of silence.)

Poetry should serve to plant the seeds of goodness and truth in people's hearts, Anna Akhmatova understood this well and was very close to Pushkin Nekrasov, who said "Life and love are short, poetry is eternal" with her ideas. The following lines prove this:

Позволь мне миру подарить

То, что любви нетленней.

(Give me the opportunity to present eternal love to the world).

His love for the world was in the form of poetry. Akhmatova's poems in a number of poetry collections such as "Vecher" (Evening), "Chetki" (Rosary) show how autobiographical they are. Several poems speak for themselves. These selections were written during Anna Akhmatova's marriage to the poet Gumilyov [10], he left his wife for days and left Tsarskoe Selo, did not show his black hair until midnight, and did not even hide his "triumphs" from Anna. Although she was a poet, she was still a woman inside. Anna Akhmatova suffered deeply, abandonment, loneliness and jealousy are felt in them:

Жгу до зари на окошке свечу

И ни о ком не тоскую,

Но не хочу, не хочу, не хочу,

Знать как целуют другую.

(I will light a candle until dawn,

I don't miss anyone

I don't want, I don't want, I don't want

Also knowing that they kiss each other.)

Such agony is known to those who have tasted betrayal. Anna Andreevna really loved her husband more than her soul, but what? Maybe she loved... However, Gumilyov, intoxicated by the fame and fortune of his poems, put Anna in a cage and always refused to recognize her talent, always emphasizing the superiority of the husband in society. The poet's heart was saddened by this. The following lines show how much she had to be patient as a woman. Such situations are not alien to many women. Because the nature of women, the views formed by society, sometimes we ourselves unwittingly follow, and it ends painfully

enough. The tragedies in Anna's life do not leave indifferent any soul suffering from oppression:

Мне не надо счастья малого,
Мужа к милой провожу
И довольного, усталого,
Спать ребенка уложу.

(I don't need half happiness, I'm sending my husband to his lover, and I'm going to put my tired child to sleep).

Но вдруг последняя сила
В синих глазах ожила:

"Хорошо, что ты отпустила,
Не всегда ты доброй была".

Anna Akhmatova's work was in every way a rebellion of hot feelings against oppression and violence, a light bursting out of the darkness, a bright star lost in the night, the light she radiated has not yet faded from literature...

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